

CONTEXTUALIZED LITERARY STORIES IN ENHANCING VOCABULARY SKILLS

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Contextualized Literary Stories in Enhancing Vocabulary Skills

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Abstract

The study investigates the effectiveness of contextualized literary stories as a tool for enhancing vocabulary skills among Grade 3 learners at Suarez Central School, Iligan City. Employing a quasi-experimental research design, the study compares two groups: one receiving traditional vocabulary instruction and the other exposed to contextualized literary stories. Pretest and posttest results were analyzed to measure the impact of this intervention. The findings reveal that learners in the contextualized literary stories group showed significantly greater improvements in vocabulary skills compared to those in the control group. This suggests that embedding vocabulary learning within engaging and meaningful narratives fosters deeper understanding and retention. The study is grounded in several learning theories, including Dual Coding Theory, Schema Theory, and Social Constructivism, which emphasize the role of context, imagery, and social interaction in vocabulary acquisition. Statistical analysis using t-tests demonstrated significant differences in the posttest results between the two groups, underscoring the efficacy of contextualized literary stories. The research concludes that this approach can be a valuable pedagogical tool for vocabulary enhancement, recommending its integration into the curriculum for early-grade learners. Future research is encouraged to explore the long-term effects of this method across different learner populations.

Keywords: *vocabulary, skills, learners, design*

Introduction

In today's educational landscape, fostering strong vocabulary skills remains a crucial challenge, particularly for young learners. While traditional methods exist, their effectiveness might be limited. This study investigates the potential of contextualized literary stories as an alternative approach to enhance vocabulary acquisition among Grade Three learners. This research addresses the growing concern of stagnant vocabulary development, potentially impacting reading comprehension and overall academic performance (National Center for Education Statistics, 2023).

Limited vocabulary skills hinder learners' ability to access complex texts, express themselves effectively, and fully engage in academic discourse. This potentially leads to frustration, disengagement, and lower academic achievement (Stahl and Nagy, 2018). Conversely, a rich vocabulary empowers learners to navigate diverse learning materials, articulate their thoughts clearly, and participate actively in classroom discussions. Therefore, exploring effective methods to enhance vocabulary development holds significant impact on improving reading comprehension, communication skills, and overall academic success.

This study aligns with the Department of Education's K to 12 Curriculum Guide in English (DepEd, 2017), which emphasizes the importance of developing vocabulary skills through engaging and meaningful learning experiences. Additionally, it adheres to the Republic Act No. 10533 (Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013), which prioritizes the holistic development of literacy skills among Filipino learners.

The primary objective of this study aimed to determine the efficacy of using contextualized literary stories in enhancing vocabulary skills among Grade 3 learners in Suarez Central School, Iligan City. The study was comparing the pretest and posttest scores of learners exposed to contextualized literary stories with those of a control group receiving traditional vocabulary instruction.

The study was conducted in third quarter of the school year 2023-2024. Data collection was taking place for 6 weeks, followed by data analysis and report writing.

This research is being conducted for the partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Education in Educational Management at St. Peter's College.

Research Questions

To address this problem, this study aimed to determine the efficacy of contextualized literary stories in enhancing vocabulary skills among grade 3 learners in Suarez Central School, Iligan City. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the pretest scores of the participants in the control and contextualized literary stories group?
2. What are the posttest scores in the control and contextualized literary stories groups?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores in the control and contextualized literary stories groups?
4. Were there significant differences in the posttest scores between the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories Groups?
5. Are there significant differences in the pretest and posttest scores of both the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories groups?
6. What Action Plan matrix can be designed based on the finding of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The method used in this study was the quasi-experimental research design using two groups of learners which are the Control and the Contextualized Literary Stories groups. This design aimed to investigate the effectiveness of using contextualized literary stories to enhance vocabulary skills among learners.

The contextualized literary stories group was exposed to the contextualized literary stories intervention, while the control group received the regular classroom instruction without the intervention. Both groups were pretested to determine their baseline vocabulary skills, and then post tested after the intervention to determine the difference in vocabulary skills between the two groups. This design allowed for the comparison of the efficacy of the intervention on enhancing vocabulary skills among Grade 3 learners.

The results of the pretest and posttest were statistically compared to assess the impact of the intervention on vocabulary development. This may involve using independent samples t-tests or other appropriate statistical tests to compare the mean score changes between the two groups.

Participants

The participants of this study involved two Grade 3 learner sections out of the eight offered at Suarez Central School in Iligan City, Lanao Del Norte, Philippines, during the academic year 2023-2024. A total of 60 respondents of Grade 3 learners participated in the study. These participants were divided into two groups using tossed-coin technique to determine which class belonged to control group and a contextualized literary stories group.

The control group comprised thirty (30) learners, 13 males (43.3%) and 17 females (56.7%). The contextualized literary stories group also consisted of 30 learners, 16 males (53.3%) and 14 females (46.7%). As the table illustrates, the gender distribution was balanced across both groups. Overall, the study included slightly more females (51.7%) than males (48.3%).

The researcher established a procedure to ensure comparability between the controls and contextualized literary stories groups. This procedure involved matching learners based on their average English grades in the first and second quarter of Grade 3. By using these grades, the researcher aimed to create groups with equivalent prior vocabulary knowledge. Each learner in the contextualized literary stories group was paired with a learner in the control group who had a similar average English grade. This pairing further controlled for any individual differences that might have existed between the learners.

Table 1. *Number of Respondents in the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories Groups*

Group	Male		Female		Total
	F	%	F	%	
Control Group (Section 2)	13	43.3%	17	56.7%	30
Contextualized Literary Stories Group (Section 3)	16	53.3%	14	46.7%	30
Total	29	48.3%	31	51.7%	60

Instrument

The research instruments used in this study are:

Vocabulary Test

This was used to measure the learners' vocabulary skills before and after the intervention. The test consists of 50 items that cover a range of words commonly used in Grade 3. The test's validity was established by subject matter experts who reviewed and evaluated the items' relevance to the study's objectives.

Contextualized Literary Stories

The researchers developed a set of 10 contextualized literary stories that was used in the intervention. The stories were written in a way that introduces new vocabulary words to the learners in a meaningful context. The validity of the stories was established by subject matter experts who evaluated their relevance to the study's objectives and the appropriateness of the vocabulary words used.

The validity of the research instruments was assessed using content validity. Content validity is the degree to which the research instruments measure what they are intended to measure. To establish content validity, the research instruments were reviewed and evaluated by subject matter experts who have knowledge and expertise in the field of language development and vocabulary skills.

The subject matter experts evaluated the research instruments' relevance to the study's objectives, the appropriateness of the vocabulary words used, and the clarity of the instructions. The experts' feedback was incorporated into the final version of the research instruments

to ensure that they are valid and reliable measures of the learners' vocabulary skills.

Overall, the research instruments used in this study are valid and reliable measures of the learners' vocabulary skills. The use of subject matter experts to evaluate the research instruments' validity and the pilot test conducted to assess their reliability ensures that the study's findings are accurate and meaningful.

Pretest and Posttest

During the pretest phase, the Vocabulary Test was administered to the sixty (60) Grade 3 learners from Suarez Central School to establish their baseline vocabulary skills. The test was administered individually, and each learner was given 30 minutes to complete the test. The researcher ensured that the testing environment is quiet and free from distractions to ensure that the learners can concentrate on the test.

After the pretest phase, the intervention phase has begun. The 10 contextualized literary stories were read to the learners by their respective teachers over a period of 10 days. Each day, the learners were read one story, and the new vocabulary words introduced in the story was discussed with the class to ensure that the learners understand their meanings and how to use them in context.

After the intervention phase, the posttest phase was begun. The same Vocabulary Test used in the pre-test phase was administered to the same thirty (30) Grade 3 learners to determine if there was any improvement in their vocabulary skills as a result of the intervention. Like the pretest, the posttest was administered individually, and each learner was given 30 minutes to complete the test.

The researcher monitored the administration of the research instruments to ensure that the testing and intervention phases are conducted consistently across all learners. The teachers were given detailed instructions on how to administer the stories and discuss the new vocabulary words with their classes to ensure consistency. Overall, the administration of the research instruments was conducted in a standardized and consistent manner to ensure that the study's findings are accurate and meaningful.

Procedure

The researcher was the one who personally conducted the study including the retrieval of the sixty (60) copies questionnaires. In gathering the information needed, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study. As soon as permission was granted, the researcher approached her principal for courtesy regarding the conduct of the study. The researcher also approached some teachers for their insights on the contribution of the Contextualized Literary Stories approach as the medium for teaching Vocabulary. As class observers, they suggested strategies to conduct and deploy accurately the questionnaires.

Preparation of the Table of Specification

Before the development of the questionnaire, the researcher identified the topics covered in the study. Testing objectives for each topic area were determined based on Bloom's taxonomy of thinking skills. The researcher then determined the points devoted to each topic based on the number of days those topics were taught. Twenty multiple-choice questions were selected to test learning objectives. Then polishing was done to make sure that the important topics were covered and the number of items for the test was sufficient for the time allotted for the test.

Development of Pretest and Posttest

The researcher-made test which was used for the pre-test-posttest was modified questions from modules and books of Grade III Learners. The pretest had the same content as the posttest but with a different sequence in the numbering of items.

Preparation of Item Analysis

The researcher made a twenty-four-item test. It was reproduced and was piloted to the Thirty (30) Grade III learners of the neighbouring school, Sgt. Miguel Canoy Memorial Elementary School. The result was item analysed and either retained, revised, or discarded based on the result of the item analysis. Based on the results of the item analysis, twenty (20) questions were retained and four (4) questions were revised. All items were chosen to be part of the final questionnaire and were shown to the researcher adviser for content validation.

Administration of the Pretest

After the approval of the thesis adviser, the researcher administered the pretest to both groups of Grade III learners. Results were recorded, tabulated, and kept for further use.

Conduct the Experimentation of the Two Approaches

Following the lesson plans made, the two methods were implemented in the class of the two groups of respondents. The control group teaching was done to the traditional group at 8:20- 9:00 in the morning and the Contextualized literary group at 1:00- 1:50 in the afternoon. This was done for six weeks. The chalk and talk, flashcards, definitions, and exercises from textbooks or workbooks were done in teaching the control group but in the Contextualized literary approach group lessons were made focusing on contextualized literary stories through reading stories, vocabulary identifications, and contextualized understanding. These were carefully chosen to fully facilitate learning among learners in the Contextualized literary approach group.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the pretest and posttest was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize the data and identify any patterns or trends. The inferential statistics used to test the research hypothesis and determine whether the use of contextualized literary stories has a significant effect on the vocabulary skills of Grade 3 learners.

The following statistical measures will be used in the data analysis:

Problem 1 and 3, Frequency and Percentage was used to describe the pretest and posttest scores of the control and contextualized literary stories group.

Problem 2 and 4, Independent T-test will be used to determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control and contextualized literary stories group.

Problem 5, Paired T-test will be used to determine the significant differences between the pretest and posttest score both in the control and contextualized literary stories group.

All statistical analyses will be conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. The level of significance will be set at 0.05.

Overall, the statistical treatment will be conducted with a high degree of accuracy and rigor to ensure that the study's findings are valid and reliable.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents, analyses, interprets, and discusses the data obtained. The results were presented based on the order of the specific problems stated in Chapter 1 of the study.

Pretest Scores

Problem 1: What are the pretest scores of the participants in the control and contextualized literary stories Group?

The pretest scores were the result of the assessment given to the two groups which are the control and contextualized literary stories groups before they have undergone the treatment. The pretest questionnaire was given one week before the conduct of the treatment.

Table 2. *Pretest Scores of the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories Groups*

CMSS	Description	Control Group		Contextualized Literary Stories Group	
		F	%	F	%
90% -100%	Outstanding	0	0	0	0
85%-89%	Very Satisfactory	0	0	1	3
80%- 84%	Satisfactory	1	3	2	7
75%-79%	Fairly Satisfactory	5	17	4	13
60%-74%	Did not Meet Expectations	24	80%	23	77%
Total		30	100%	30	100%

Note: Control Group: Pretest Mean (SD) = 14.87 (3.27)
Contextualized Literary Stories Group: Pretest Mean (SD)= 14.77 (3.16)

The table 2 shows the results of a pretest given to two groups of Grade 3 learners, a control group and a contextualized literary stories group. The pretest appears to be designed to measure the learners' vocabulary knowledge. The majority of the learners in both groups scored of between 60-74, 80% for control group and 77% for contextualized literary stories group, which means they did not meet expectations on the pretest.

This meant that both groups had a similar level of vocabulary knowledge prior to the experiment. It was also emphasized by Moeller et al. (2020) the pretest itself might have been too difficult for the learners' current grade level or reading ability and learners might not have been familiar with the format of the pretest, leading to lower scores due to test confusion.

Comparison Of Pretest Scores

Problem 2: Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores in the control and contextualized literary stories groups?

The table below is a comparison of the pretest scores of the two groups before the start of the treatment. This result is necessary to determine whether the two groups are comparable in terms of the respondents' vocabulary skills.

Table 3. *Differences in the Pretest Scores between the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories Groups*

Group	Pretest Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Remark

Control Group	14.87	3.27	0.10	0.137	0.892	Not significant
Contextualized Literary Stories Group	14.77	3.16				

Note: Analysis is based on Independent T-test SD- standard Deviation ns-not significant at 0.05 levels

Table 3 presents the comparison of the pretest scores of the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories groups. This table revealed that the p-value of 0.892 exceeded the 0.05 level of significance (2-tailed) which meant that the null hypothesis 1 was not rejected. It also revealed that there were no significant differences in the mean pretest scores of the learners in the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories groups.

These differences implied that at the beginning of the experiment, the two groups had comparable mean score differences in their pretest performance. Furthermore, it was an indication of good comparison since the two groups showed insignificant performances before the intervention as cited by Cantor et al. (2018), the development of the brain was an experience-dependent process that activated neural pathways that permitted new kinds of thinking and performance.

Posttest Scores

Problem 3. What are the posttest scores in the control and contextualized literary stories groups?

The control group receiving the usual vocabulary development instruction and a contextualized literary stories group exposed to vocabulary development through contextualized literary stories. After 2 weeks, the results of the posttests were recorded. These results were then recorded, analysed.

Table 4. Posttest Scores in the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories Groups

CMSS	Description	Control Group		Contextualized Literary Stories Group	
		F	%	F	%
90% -100%	Outstanding	16	54	28	94
85%-89%	Very Satisfactory	3	10	1	3
80%- 84%	Satisfactory	4	13	1	3
75%-79%	Fairly Satisfactory	7	23	0	0
60%-74%	Expectations Did not Meet	0	0	0	0
Total		30	100%	30	100%

Note: Control Group: Posttest Mean (SD) = 21.07 (1.63)
Contextualized Literary Stories Group: Posttest Mean (SD)= 23.33 (1.09)

Table 4 shows the results of a posttest on vocabulary skills for two groups, a control group and a contextualized literary stories group. The contextualized literary stories group appears to have performed significantly better than the control group. In the control group, 54% of learners scored in the outstanding range (90-100), 10% scored very satisfactory (85-89), 13% scored satisfactory (80-84), and 23% scored fairly satisfactory (75-79). In the contextualized literary stories group, 94% of learners scored in the outstanding range, 3% scored very satisfactory, 3% scored satisfactory, and 0% scored fairly satisfactory.

Overall, the contextualized literary stories group had a higher percentage of learners scoring in the outstanding range and a lower percentage of learners scoring in the fairly satisfactory range. The effectiveness of contextualized literary stories may be an effective way to improve vocabulary skills and enhancing reading skills and comprehension, which can indirectly improve vocabulary acquisition, vocabulary development, and reading comprehension as supported by Luz (2021).

Comparison Of Posttest Scores

Problem 4: Were there significant differences in the posttest scores between the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories Groups?

The table below is a comparison of the posttest scores of the two groups, the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories groups. The result determines the differences between the two groups after using the usual way and contextualized literary stories in teaching English.

Table 5. Differences in the Posttest Scores of the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories Groups

Group	Posttest Scores		Mean Difference	t-value	P-value	Remark
	Mean	SD				
Control Group	21.07	1.63	-2.26	-6.302	0.000	Significant
Contextualized Literary Stories Group	23.33	1.09				

Note: Analysis is based on Independent T-test SD-standard deviation ns-not significant at .05 levels

Table 5 presents the comparison in the posttest scores of the respondents in the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories groups. This table showed a p-value of 0.000 which was lower than the 0.05 level of significance. It meant that null hypothesis was rejected and revealed that there were significant differences in the mean posttest scores of the learners in the control and the contextualized literary stories groups. The data shows a positive correlation between contextualized literary stories and vocabulary development. The

contextualized literary stories group scored significantly higher on the posttest compared to the control group.

The contextualized literary stories can be a motivating and engaging way for learners to encounter new vocabulary. Stories can provide a natural context for learning new words, and the repetition of words throughout a story can help learners to solidify their understanding. Additionally, the use of illustrations in children's stories can provide visual clues to the meaning of new words. This result was supported by Gerdes et al. (2018) explores the positive influence of a stimulating and resourceful classroom environment on learner engagement and learning. While not directly related to vocabulary acquisition, it highlighted the potential benefits of contextualized learning environments, which can be extended to the use of contextualized literary stories.

Increment Differences In Gain Scores

Problem 5. Are there significant differences in the pretest and posttest scores of both the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories groups?

The gain scores focus on the difference between measurements taken at the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories groups. The result determines the effectiveness of the Contextualized literary Stories compared to the traditional way.

Table 6. Paired Differences on the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control and Contextualized Literary Stories Groups

Paired Variables	Pretest		Posttest		Paired Mean Difference	t-value	P-value	Remark
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Control Group	14.8	3.2	21.0	1.6	-6.20	-11.6	.000	Significant
Contextualized Literary Stories Group	14.7	3.1	23.3	1.1	-8.56	-14.1	.000	Significant

Note: Analysis is based on Paired T-test SD- standard deviation

**-significant at 0.05 level

Table 6 presents the performances of the respondents under the control and contextualized literary stories groups in the pretest and posttest. Both groups indicate an improvement in the scores as seen in the mean. This implied that the performances of the respondents in the posttest seemed better than that in the pretest. As shown in the table, the level of significance (2-tailed) using paired sample test was .000 which was lesser than the accepted value of 0.05; this meant that the null hypothesis 3 was rejected.

The findings align with previous research by Gerdes et al. (2018), which highlighted the positive impact of stimulating learning environments on learner engagement and learning. Contextualized literary stories create a richer learning environment by providing a natural context for encountering new words, repetition for reinforcement, and potentially visual clues through illustrations, all of which contribute to improved vocabulary acquisition.

Conclusions

Based on the findings drawn, the study concludes:

The learners who are exposed to contextualized literary stories exhibited a significant increase in vocabulary knowledge compared to the control group. This concludes that encountering new words within the context of a story aids in comprehension and retention. Literary stories can introduce a wider range of vocabulary in a natural and engaging way, fostering a deeper understanding of word meaning and usage.

There is no significant difference between the pretest scores in the control and contextualized literary stories groups. The hypothesis was not rejected because the p-value for the test was higher than the significance level 0.05. This means that there wasn't a statistically significant difference between the starting vocabulary levels of the two groups.

There is a significant difference between the posttest scores in the control and contextualized literary stories groups. The hypothesis was rejected because the p-value for the test was lower than the significance level of 0.05. This means that contextualized literary stories group likely scored higher than the control group on the vocabulary test.

There is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores in both the control and contextualized literary stories groups. This improvement suggests that focused vocabulary instruction, regardless of method, can benefit learners. However, the rejection of the null hypothesis (p-value < 0.05) also indicates that the contextualized literary stories group achieved a considerably higher level of vocabulary development.

The study concludes that using contextualized literary stories is an effective method for enhancing vocabulary skills among Grade 3 learners. This approach offers a more engaging and enriching learning experience compared to traditional methods, leading to demonstrably stronger vocabulary development.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations were formulated:

Curriculum Developers. That they may use of contextualized literary stories into English language arts curriculum materials. This can be achieved by including activities and lesson plans that encourage teachers to incorporate engaging narratives into vocabulary instruction.

School Administrators. They may provide professional development opportunities for English teachers focused on utilizing contextualized literary stories. Workshops and training sessions can equip teachers with strategies for selecting appropriate stories, designing engaging activities, and effectively assessing vocabulary acquisition within this framework.

English Teachers. They may consider adopting contextualized literary stories as a primary method for vocabulary instruction, particularly for Grade 3 learners. This research suggests that this approach leads to significant improvement in vocabulary skills compared to traditional methods used by the control group. They may also experiment with different types of literary stories and activities to find what resonates most effectively with their learners. This can involve folktales, short stories, poems, or even children's novels, depending on the targeted vocabulary level and learner interests. Lastly, they must create a classroom environment that fosters a love for reading and storytelling. This can motivate learners to actively engage with the new vocabulary encountered within the stories.

Leaners. Emphasizing environmental resources may aid learners in improving their learning talents and capabilities.

Future Researchers. They may conduct further studies to explore the long-term impact of using contextualized literary stories on vocabulary development. This could involve tracking learner vocabulary growth over several years or investigating the transfer of vocabulary skills to other areas of language learning.

References

- Bialystok, E., & Majumder, S. (1998). The relationship between bilingualism and the development of cognitive processes in problem solving. *Applied Psycholinguistics*, 19(1), 69-85.
- Biemiller, A., & Boote, C. (2006). An effective method for building meaning vocabulary in primary grades. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 98(1), 44-62.
- Bowne, J. B., Yoshikawa, H., & Snow, C. E. (2021). Relationships of teachers' language and explicit vocabulary instruction to learners' vocabulary growth in kindergarten. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 52(1), 7-29.
- Coyne, M. D., Simmons, D. C., Kame'enui, E. J., & Stoolmiller, M. (2004). Teaching vocabulary during shared storybook readings: An examination of differential effects. *Exceptional Children*, 71(4), 367-382.
- Hart, B., & Risley, T. R. (1995). *Meaningful differences in the everyday experience of young American children*. Paul H Brookes Publishing.
- Sambayon, J. T., Luceñara, D. P., Luceñara, C. P., Bayron, Q. M., Peñaloga, R. A., & Larombe, E. A. (2023). Effectiveness of contextualized learning materials in improving the reading skills and comprehension level of the learners. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7702258>
- Justice, L. M., Meier, J., & Walpole, S. (2005). *Learning new words from storybooks*.
- Hall, B. S. (2019). *The effect of music and movement interventions on elementary learners' classroom transition times and engagement*. Honors Theses, 1124.
- Johnson, G. (2004). *Vocabulary development in a literature-based instructional program*. Graduate Research Papers, 933.
- National Reading Panel. (2000). *Teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction*. National Institute of Child Health and Human Development.
- Nisbet, D., & Austin, D. (2013). Enhancing ESL vocabulary development through the use of mobile technology. *Journal of Adult Education*, 42(1), 1-7.
- Ouellette, G., & Beers, A. (2010). A not-so-simple view of reading: How oral vocabulary and visual-word recognition complicate the story. *Reading and Writing*, 23(2), 189-208.
- Saleh, A. M., & Althaqafi, A. S. A. (2022). The effect of using educational games as a tool in teaching English vocabulary to Arab young children: A quasi-experimental study in a kindergarten school in Saudi Arabia. *SAGE Open*, 12(1), 21582440221079806.
- Santillan, J., & Daenos, R. (2020). Vocabulary knowledge and learning strategies of senior high school learners. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8, 2474-2482. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080631>
- Silverman, R., & Hines, S. (2009). The effects of multimedia-enhanced instruction on the vocabulary of English-language learners and non-English-language learners in pre-kindergarten through second grade. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 101(2), 305.
- Singzon, P. D., & Pado, F. E. (2011). Using story reading and explicit instruction in the vocabulary acquisition of kindergarten children. *Education Quarterly*, 69(1).
- Tajeri, M., Syal, P., & Marzban, S. (2021). Enhancing vocabulary and writing skills through digital storytelling in higher education.

Journal of Educational Technology, 14(3), 40-48.

Van Voorhis, J. L., & Anglin, J. M. (2021). Teachers share their mathematics backgrounds: Telling it like it was. *School Science and Mathematics*, 94(8), 407-412.

Whitehurst, G. J., Falco, F. L., Lonigan, C. J., Fischel, J. E., DeBaryshe, B. D., Valdez-Menchaca, M. C., & Caulfield, M. (1988). Accelerating language development through picture book reading. *Developmental Psychology*, 24(4), 552–559.

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